

Enhancement of Lipase CAL-A Selectivity by Protein Engineering for the Hydrolysis of Erucic Acid from *Crambe* Oil

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The aim of this study is to pursue the identification and characterization of different CAL-A variants displaying higher specificity toward erucic acid than CAL-A wild type (wt). A careful analysis of the data generated from previously created site-directed saturation libraries reveals several variants that display a higher preference for the hydrolysis of *p*-nitrophenyl (*p*NP)-erucate over *p*NP-oleate than the wt. The best three candidates (CAL-A V238D, V238Y, and V286N) are applied in biocatalysis using both *Crambe* oil and ethyl ester derivatives. When acting on *Crambe* oil, these CAL-A variants are as efficient as CAL-A wt in terms of C22:1 enrichment and product recovery independently of the temperature (enrichment and recovery values between 70–76% and 67–79% at 37 °C, and between 71–73% and 61–75% at 50 °C). In contrast, hydrolysis of *Crambe* ethyl esters leads to substantially increased accumulations of C22:1 and recovery values (V238Y: 78% enrichment and 92% recovery; V286N: 83% enrichment and 91% recovery) when using CAL-A V238Y and CAL-A V286N compared to CAL-A wt (78% enrichment, 60% recovery) in the free fatty acid fraction.

Practical Applications: This study describes the enhancement of lipase CAL-A selectivity for the isolation and recovery of erucic acid (C22:1) from plant oil or its ethyl ester derivatives. Hence, this approach could represent a more eco-friendly alternative for its application in processes where the erucic acid is used as building block, such as the production of surfactants or polymers.

1. Introduction

Protein engineering is defined as the process of manipulating the structure of an existing protein to provide it with a desired property. Therefore, this approach has revealed itself as the most important method to overcome the limitations of natural enzymes as biocatalysts in chemical biotechnology as previously pointed out in a review: “in the past, an enzyme-based process was designed around the limitations of the enzyme; today, the enzyme is engineered to fit the process specifications.”^[1] Consequently, the application of protein engineering shows great potential to obtain suitable enzymes for industrial processes, thus being widely investigated for this purpose.^[2–5]

In particular, there is a growing industrial interest in the development of biocatalysts for their implementation in lipid biotechnology. This field aims to develop greener reaction technologies by merging the use of both, renewable raw material sources as vegetable oils and enzymes as biocatalysts to produce fuels and chemicals.^[6,7] Predictably, since their natural function is the hydrolysis of triacylglycer-

ides (TAG), the most commonly employed enzymes in oleochemistry are lipases (EC 3.1.1.3). Additionally, this class of enzymes offers an interesting advantage for their applicability due to the particular chemo-, regio-, and stereoselectivity that each lipase displays.^[8] Hence, the most appropriate biocatalyst could be chosen to directly fulfill the specific requirements of a determined biotransformation, or to serve as template for protein engineering to further optimize its features.^[9–11] In this sense, due to the unique architecture of its substrate binding site, which forms a tunnel like cavity, *Candida antarctica* lipase A (CAL-A) has been proven to be an excellent candidate to undergo protein engineering approaches to tailor a desired property and several examples have been described in the literature.^[12–18] For instance, in our previous work enrichment of erucic and gondoic fatty acids was accomplished from *Crambe* and *Camelina* seed oils.^[17,18] These compounds are naturally present in high concentration in the oils of plants of the genera *Cruciferae*^[19] and are relevant building blocks in industry for the production of surfactants,

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polymers (e.g., erucamide), and lubricants.^[20] To achieve that purpose, two different Lipase-catalyzed strategies could be envisioned (**Scheme 1**): i) hindering the hydrolysis of this desired fatty acid while all the others are hydrolyzed or ii) hydrolyzing selectively C22:1, leaving all the other fatty acids as esters. The first strategy would cause an increase of the erucic acid concentration in the esterified fatty acid (EFA) fraction, whereas the second one would entail its accumulation in the free fatty acid (FFA) fraction. As it seemed to be the most straightforward approach, the first strategy was previously pursued for the enrichment of erucic and gondoic acids by establishing a hydrolysis cutoff where the lipase could only act on FA shorter than C20. Interestingly, during the screening of the different mutagenesis libraries, several variants were identified with increased predilection for the hydrolysis of erucic acid over the shorter oleic acid substrates when compared to the parental enzyme.^[17,18] Hence, they constitute good candidates to explore the second alternative described above.

Concerning the erucic acid source to be used, as aforementioned, *Crambe* oil represents an outstanding starting material since it is mainly composed of this compound (58.7%), while oleic, linoleic, and linolenic fatty acids (C₁₈ unsaturated FA) embody almost all the rest of the mixture (31.2%).^[17,18] From a practical point of view, plant oils can be used as substrates in their original TAG form, or after a non-selective transesterification step with a short chain alcohol, with fatty acid methyl and ethyl esters being the most common derivatives manufactured. In the first case, the use of TAG would avoid the transesterification stage to synthesize the ester derivatives, concomitantly saving time and resources. However, it must be taken into account that the utilization of ethyl ester derivatives in industry may involve some alternative advantages, including the lower density, viscosity, and melting points displayed when compared to the initial oil.^[23–25] Generally, this helps to avoid the necessity to work under higher temperatures to prevent both, the plugging of the pipelines and the formation of undesired aggregates during biocatalysis. Concomitantly, lower temperatures usually imply higher stability of the biocatalyst. Another potential benefit is that FAEE themselves constitute a valuable group of organic molecules that is widely employed, for example, as high-value lubricants, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, or

bio-diesel.^[26,27] Thus, ethyl esters separated at the end of the biotransformation could be directly guided toward new processes for the obtaining of these compounds. In addition, lipase selectivity could be potentiated when acting on small esters instead of on the more sterically challenging triacylglycerides.

Therefore, the aim of the present study was to verify the enhanced preference toward C22:1 of the previously mentioned CAL-A variants and characterize their substrate selectivity. Moreover, the applicability of the best variants was studied for the enrichment of erucic acid in the FFA fraction instead of the EFA when using *Crambe* oil and *Crambe* ethyl ester derivatives as starting substrates.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Materials

Unless stated otherwise all chemicals were purchased from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland), Sigma (Steinheim, Germany), Merck (Darmstadt, Germany), VWR (Hannover, Germany), or Carl Roth (Karlsruhe, Germany). Primers were synthesized by Sigma (Steinheim, Germany) and Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA). Sequencing was performed by Eurofins MWG Operon (Luxembourg, Luxembourg). *Escherichia coli* TOP10 strain was obtained from Invitrogen (Carlsbad, CA, USA) and *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) C41 strain was purchased from Lucigen (Middletown, USA). Plasmid pPICZα was purchased from Invitrogen (Carlsbad, USA).

2.2. Methods

The following assays were performed as previously described: i) re-screening of the CAL-A variants that showed higher activity toward pNP-C22:1; ii) creation of pPICZα-CALA-His vectors containing the desired mutations (Table S1 and S2, Supporting Information); iii) overexpression in *P. pastoris* (Table S3, Figure S1, Supporting Information); iv) protein concentration determination; and v) hydrolytic activity toward pNP-esters of different chain length.^[17,18]

Scheme 1. Possible concepts to enrich erucic acid either as (i) ester or (ii) free fatty acid using selective lipase catalysis.

2.2.1. Erucic Acid Enrichment Reactions Using *Crambe* Oil and *Crambe* Ethyl Esters

Fatty acid enrichment reactions were performed as described previously^[17,18] with slight modifications. First, an initial estimation of the amount of lipase to be added to the reactions was made by checking the rate of hydrolysis of *Crambe* oil with 0.01, 0.1, 1, or 10 U of enzyme (CAL-A V238D, CAL-A V238Y, or CAL-A V286N) after 4 h reaction at 37 °C. A blank reaction without enzyme served to check for autohydrolysis of the oil. Once estimated, the enzyme units required to hydrolyze ≈10–40% of substrate after 4 h, enrichment reactions were carried out by analyzing the hydrolysis of either *Crambe* oil (triglyceride) or *Crambe* FAEE derivatives. When using *Crambe* oil as substrate, reactions were performed using 10 U of CAL-A variants (CAL-A V238D, CAL-A V238Y, or CAL-A V286N) at two different temperatures, 37 and 50 °C. *Crambe* FAEE enrichment reactions were performed at 37 °C using either 10 (CAL-A V238D, CAL-A V238Y, or CAL-A V286N), 50 (CAL-A V286N), or 100 U (CAL-A V238D) of CAL-A variants. Fatty acid enrichment along time was measured by analyzing time point samples at 0, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 24 h. All reactions were carried out in triplicates and each time sample reaction was performed in a 2 mL polypropylene tube containing 250 μL of the corresponding substrate, the desired amount of enzyme and distilled water to a final volume of 310 μL. Reactions were shaken at 1400 rpm while incubated at the required temperature. As substrate, an emulsion containing 5 g of either *Crambe* oil or *Crambe* ethyl esters (Solutex, Zaragoza, Spain), 2 g gum arabic, and 100 mL buffer 50 mM sodium phosphate with 1 mM NaCl at pH 7.5 was prepared by shearmixing at 24 000 rpm for 2 min (Ultra Turrax T25 basic, IKA Labor Technik, Staufen, Germany). Enzyme solutions were prepared using the lyophilized supernatants from the fermentation of *P. pastoris* GS115 strains overexpressing CAL-A variants. Prior to their use, enzyme solutions were dialyzed and their activity was determined toward *p*NP-erucate as previously described. To stop the reactions samples were vortexed after adding 25 μL of HCl (4 N) and stored at –20 °C until extraction. After extraction of the samples evaluation of the hydrolyses was performed by TLC as described.^[17,18]

2.2.2. Analysis of the Fatty Acid Composition in the Different Oil Fractions

In order to quantify the reaction mixture composition, reaction samples were treated as described in our previous work.^[17,18,21,22] Briefly, samples were extracted with 250 mL diethylether containing as internal standards tripentadecanoate (2 mM) and either tridecanoic acid (2 mM) or tridecanoate ethyl ester (2 mM) depending on whether the hydrolyzed substrate were the TAG from *Crambe* oil or the FAEE derivatives, respectively. Each sample was extracted two more times with 500 μL pure diethylether and the joined organic phases were dried with anhydrous Na₂SO₄. After evaporation of the organic solvent the residue was resuspended in 1 mL anhydrous *n*-hexane and split in two aliquots. To analyze the fatty acids present in the mixture they must be in the form of methyl or

ethyl ester derivatives (FAME and FAEE). Therefore, when quantifying the composition involving *Crambe* oil two different methylation methods were necessary: the sodium methoxide method and the methanolic hydrogensulfate method. The sodium methoxide method allowed the selective methylation of the EFA fraction, while the methanolic hydrogensulfate method was used to methylate all fatty acids indistinctively. Hence, after derivatizing each of the aforementioned aliquots with a different method it was possible to determine the total FA composition and the composition of the EFA. Moreover, the composition of the FFA fraction was calculated by subtracting the FA present in the EFA to the total FA in the mixture. In contrast, when quantifying the composition of aliquots extracted from *Crambe* FAEE reactions only the methanolic hydrogensulfate method was required since it was possible to measure the FAEE directly.

Peak identification by comparison with the corresponding standards and fatty acid composition of each of the samples was evaluated concerning the percentage of each FA and the theoretical recovery which is defined as the amount of (in this case) erucic acid (C22:1) present in the enriched fraction in comparison to the total amount of C22:1 in the sample.

3. Results and Discussion

A re-screening of the potentially interesting variants from the mutant libraries previously created^[17] was performed (Supporting Information). Those that displayed better selectivity were sequenced (Table S1, Supporting Information), overexpressed and their hydrolytic profile toward different chain length *p*NP-FA derivatives was studied (Figure S2, Supporting Information). This preliminary analysis of the overexpression and *p*NP ester hydrolysis revealed variants CAL-A V238D, CAL-A V238Y, and CAL-A V286N as the most interesting candidates for further studies for the erucic acid enrichment (Figure 1). As starting

Figure 1. CAL-A crystal structure (PDB: 3GUU) with a molecule of erucic acid docked into the binding pocket. The most relevant features for this research are highlighted: i) the lid is displayed in pink; ii) the flap is shown in light purple; iii) the catalytic amino acids Ser184, Asp334, and His364 are presented in red; iv) the selected amino acids in the binding pocket for protein engineering (V238, V286, and V290) are brown; and v) the unexpected amino acid changes are colored in gray.

material two different substrates were investigated: *Crambe* oil (i.e., TAG) and its FAEE derivatives.

3.1. Biocatalysis Using *Crambe* Ethyl Esters as Substrate

First, characterization of the potential of CAL-A variants V238D, V238Y, and V286N was studied toward *Crambe* FAEE derivatives. Initially 10 U (measured toward *p*NP-C22:1) of each one of the lipase variants were added to the reaction. As it can be seen in **Figure 2A**, after 24 h the percentage of FA hydrolyzed widely varied depending on the enzyme employed. CAL-A V238Y achieved the highest hydrolysis of FAEE, being able to convert $\approx 72\%$ of the ethyl esters, while this value decreased for CAL-A V286N and V238D to 45 and 31%, respectively. Therefore, in order to augment the hydrolysis attained, biotransformations with CAL-A V286N and V238D were repeated adding five- and tenfold of the amount of each lipase (i.e., 50 U of CAL-V286N and 100 U of V238D). Interestingly, in spite of such an increase in the amount of units added, CAL-A V238D hydrolysis values remained similar to the ones previously obtained (**Figure 2A**). This indicates an equilibrium threshold at about 30% conversion for this variant. In contrast, this time CAL-A V286N showed higher hydrolysis of the substrate, up to 67% of the total ester content.

Concerning the enrichment of C22:1 achieved, under these conditions all of them showed a similar pattern: C22:1 represented almost 100% of the FA forming the FFA at the beginning of the biocatalysis and then very slowly decreased as the substrate hydrolysis advanced. This fact can be explained due to the change in fatty acid composition in the esterified fraction as the reaction progressed, thus influencing the lipase selectivity as the less preferred fatty acids become so predominant in the substrate that the lipase will act on them as well. Nevertheless, this decrease in C22:1 concentration in the FFA fraction represented less than 3% change for hydrolysis values between 17 and 61% for CAL-A V238Y, or less than 5% for CAL-A V286N in a similar range (6 to 67%). Hence, enrichments of $\approx 80\%$ were maintained by these two variants, even when the substrate hydrolysis was higher than 60%.

Consequently, this was reflected on the theoretical recoveries accomplished, being this value defined as the amount of C22:1

present in the enriched fraction in comparison to the total amount of C22:1 in the sample (in both FFA and EFA) (**Figure 2B**). The values obtained were notoriously good, excluding CAL-A V238D, which did not exceed 42% of recovery yield from the total C22:1 initially present in the FAEE mixture. For instance, when using CAL-A V238Y C22:1 recovery reached 92% for an enrichment of 78% in the FFA fraction. Alternatively, for a similar value of recovery (91%) CAL-A V286N displayed better C22:1 enrichment (83%). It is noteworthy that by stopping the reaction at the proper percentage of substrate hydrolysis a FFA fraction with higher concentration in C22:1 can be recovered, however this entails a toll on terms of the recovery yield of C22:1.

When comparing these results with those previously obtained for CAL-A wt (10 U measured toward *p*NP-C14:0; roughly for comparison purposes, the activity displayed by CAL-A wt toward *p*NP-C22:1 is 80% of the activity toward *p*NP-C14:0), it can be observed that for similar values of C22:1 enrichment, that is, 78%, the wt enzyme achieved a recovery of 60% while in the process catalyzed by CAL-A V238Y up to 92% of the total initial C22:1 was present in the enriched fraction. Similarly, C22:1 concentrations at the highest recovery values for CAL-A wt (87%), V238Y (92%), and V286N (91%), represent 72, 78, and 83%, correspondingly. Additionally, it must be taken into consideration that the improvement in enrichment and recovery is also true when taking into account the CAL-A variants previously designed for the hydrolysis of FA shorter than C₂₀.^[17,18] In this sense, the best variants among them were V1 and V19, which displayed an enrichment of C22:1 82% (74% recovery) and 80% (48% recovery), respectively, in the EFA fraction after dosing optimization.^[18]

Therefore, the newly characterized lipase variants V238Y and V286N were able to reach better enrichment and recovery values regarding to the previously reported EFA-enriching CAL-A variants and to the parental enzyme when using *Crambe* FAEE as substrate.

3.2. Biocatalysis Using *Crambe* Oil as Substrate

Second, feasibility of using *Crambe* oil as triacylglycerides was studied for the three CAL-A variants. Initially, biocatalytic conversion of the oil was performed similarly as for the FAEE

Figure 2. A) Content of C22:1 in FFA fraction depending on *Crambe* FAEE hydrolysis and B) theoretical recovery percentage of C22:1 that could be achieved with a determined C22:1 enrichment in the FFA fraction. The theoretical recovery is defined as the amount of C22:1 present in the enriched fraction in comparison to the total amount of C22:1 in the sample.

(10 U of enzyme, 37 °C). In this experiment the hydrolysis reached also varied considerably depending on the CAL-A variant, representing 63% for V238D, 96% for V238Y, and 65% for V286N (Figure 3A). These values differ from those previously obtained for the FAEE, where the final hydrolysis percentages were lower. Especially high in comparison was the hydrolyzed fraction with V238D, which was twice the percentage achieved with the ethyl ester derivatives.

As already observed, C22:1 concentration slowly diminished in the FFA fraction as the hydrolysis of the TAG progressed. Nevertheless, enrichment of C22:1 from *Crambe* oil in the FFA fraction could be observed for the selected CAL-A variants. Thus, between 63 and 65% hydrolysis, these variants allowed for C22:1 enrichments of 70–73%. This corresponds to theoretical recoveries of 75, 73, and 79% for variants V238D, V238Y, and V286N, respectively (Figure 3B). These results were comparable to those reported using CAL-A wt (78% enrichment and 67% recovery) and the best EFA-enriching variant, V1 (76% C22:1 enrichment with 72% recovery) in similar conditions.^[18] Likewise, the level of enrichment attained could be increased by stopping the reaction at an earlier stage, although at the expense of the recovery yield.

The fact that the accumulation of C22:1 in the FFA fraction catalyzed by the CAL-A variants when using the triacylglyceride substrate was lower than when using the FAEE could be due to the observed formation of aggregates during the reaction. The appearance of precipitates can be explained attending to the different melting temperature of the products and intermediates that were formed a long the process. For instance, while the melting temperature is below 37 °C for *Crambe* oil as a whole mixture, for dierucin and monoerucin it is above 45 °C.^[19,28] From a practical point of view this translates into the removal by precipitation of the monoacyl and diacyl derivatives that are rich in the desired fatty acid, making it impossible for the lipase to access them. An alternative to overcome this problem could be to incubate the biocatalysis reactions at higher temperatures, facilitating the solubility of the compounds with more demanding melting temperatures. The new reaction temperature was chosen based on a prior study where CAL-A wt demonstrated that its highest hydrolysis rate for *Crambe* oil was at 50 °C in comparison to 37, 60, and 70 °C, while retaining good values of enrichment and recovery.^[18]

Analysis of the results obtained showed an increase of the catalysis rate at 50 °C in comparison to 37 °C. In this case, a more similar final substrate hydrolysis for V238D (76%), V238Y (88%), and V286N (82%) was achieved (Figure 3A). Meanwhile, concentrations of C22:1 in the FFA fraction were related once again with the degree of hydrolysis of the oil and the recovery yield of the desired FA. A reasonably good compromise could be achieved by all the variants, resulting in enrichments of 71% for V238Y (hydrolysis of 69%) and 73% for both, V238D (hydrolysis of 51%) and V286N (hydrolysis of 62%). Recoveries of C22:1 at these time points corresponded to 78, 61, and 74%, respectively (Figure 3B). Therefore, the values obtained with the CAL-A variants at both temperatures were very similar, although slightly better at the highest temperature. Additionally, these results indicated that C22:1 enrichment from *Crambe* oil is equally efficient for both, CAL-A wt (61% hydrolysis, 73% enrichment, and 75% recovery) and the new variants, hence being advantageous in terms of C22:1 recovery regarding the best EFA-enriching variant CAL-A V238L/V290L (76% enrichment and 72% recovery).

In spite of the good nature of the results, this reveals a difference with the behavior demonstrated by variants V238D, V238Y, and V286N during the biocatalysis using the ethyl ester derivatives. Especially for variants CAL-A V238Y and CAL-A V286N, which were able to produce enrichments around 80% with recovery yields above 90%. As aforementioned, a plausible explanation would be a negative influence on the selectivity of the bulkier complex of the triacylglycerides in opposition to the single-chain fatty acid ester derivatives. Interestingly, a decrease in erucic acid enrichment could also be observed during the biocatalytic hydrolysis of *Crambe* oil when compared to the ethyl ester derivatives using the best previous variants (V1 and V19), while this value remain stable for CAL-A wt. Unfortunately, the structural reasons could not be elucidated, since the crystal structure of CAL-A is only available in its closed (inactive) form without any triacylglyceride bound.

4. Conclusions

In summary the research described here demonstrates the enhancement of CAL-A selectivity toward the enrichment of

Figure 3. A) Content of C22:1 in FFA fraction depending on *Crambe* oil hydrolysis and B) theoretical recovery percentage of C22:1 that could be achieved with a determined C22:1 enrichment in the FFA fraction. The theoretical recovery is defined as the amount of C22:1 present in the enriched fraction in comparison to the total amount of C22:1 in the sample.

erucic acid via enzyme engineering. Specifically, application of variants CAL-A V238Y and CAL-A V286N has proven to be a more suitable alternative to achieve higher final C22:1 concentrations and recoveries in the FFA when using Crambe ethyl ester derivatives (V238Y: 78% enrichment and 92% recovery; V286N: 83% enrichment and 91% recovery, compared to CAL-A wt 78% enrichment, 60% recovery).

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Abbreviations

CAL-A, *Candida antarctica* lipase A; pNP, para-nitrophenol; C22:1, erucic acid; C20:1, gondoic acid; TAG, triacylglycerides; FA, fatty acid; EFA, esterified fatty acid fraction; FFA, free fatty acid fraction; FAEE, fatty acid ethyl esters; FAME, fatty acid methyl esters.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.

Keywords

biocatalysis, *Candida antarctica* lipase A, erucic acid enrichment, lipid modification, protein engineering

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